
The ‘Ungoverned Spaces’ and Armed Conflict in the North West Nigeria: Kinetic or Non-Kinetic Approach to Attain Peace in the Region?

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ABSTRACT

The north west of Nigeria has been constantly on the news for the negative created by the absurdity and horrendous activities of the bandits, kidnappers, cattle rustlers, the Fulani gunmen, and ‘unknown gunmen’ wreaking havoc in the region. It has become a common occurrence for the gunmen to storm villages, killing, abducting and burning down houses and farms of the rural people and occasionally making incursions to towns and cities kidnapping students and people for ransom. This has created some security challenges which the Federal Government of Nigeria has been battling with for over a decade. The Government has taken the kinetic measures to solve the armed conflict problem in the region while non-kinetic approach has been relegated or unutilised. The focus of this paper is to establish the relationship between the ‘ungoverned spaces’ and armed conflict as well as identifying some salient non-kinetic approaches that can be combined with the already established kinetic methods to resolve the armed violence in the sub-region.

KEYWORDS: ungoverned spaces; armed conflict; kinetic & non-kinetic; peace.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the Nigeria state has been engulfed in armed conflict involving the Fulani militants, bandits, kidnappers, ‘unknown gun men’ and the Nigerian military resulting in deaths, destruction of villages and towns and high number of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), particularly in the north west of the country. The insurgency in the north east is arguably the spill-over effect on armed violence in the north west as the bandits continue to create human misery in abduction for ransom, burning down of villages, markets, farms and wanton killings of innocent people and forcing the villagers to pay taxes especially to the bandits. The activities of the bandits in the north west has created a lot of insecurity in which many communities have been abandoned by the rural dwellers as they are being kidnapped, killed or their women and school girls being abducted to serve as sex slaves in different kidnappers’ camps dotted the forests in the region. The impacts of banditry on local populations in the Northwest region have been equally devastating. Bandits were reportedly responsible for more Nigerian deaths than Boko Haram, armed robbers, kidnappers and gangs combined, and were reportedly responsible for 47.5% of all violent deaths in 2019 (Daily Trust; 2019). The usual approach of the Federal Government of Nigeria was the deployment of the Military to combat the armed men terrorizing the region. This approach has been going on for a decade without a tangible result in bringing to an end the armed conflict in the region. The intention of this work is to advocate for the introduction of non-kinetic approach or the combination of kinetic and non-kinetic approaches to resolve the armed conflict ravaging the north west of Nigeria. The paper attempts to establish the linkages between the ‘ungoverned spaces’ and armed conflict; identified various kinetic measures already applied; and identify non-kinetic measures that can help to resolve the armed violence as well as recommendations/way forward to bring a lasting peace to the region.

DEFINITION OF THE TERMS

‘Ungoverned Spaces’ are places where the state or central government is unable or unwilling to extend control, effectively govern, or influence the local population, and where a provincial, local, tribal, or autonomous government does not fully or effectively govern, due to inadequate governance capacity, insufficient political will, gaps in legitimacy, the presence of conflict, or restrictive norms of behaviour. Ungoverned areas should be assumed to include under-governed, ill-governed, contested, and exploitable areas (Taylor, A. 2016). The existing ungoverned environment is driven by incessant conflict in a state or region such as northern Nigeria where Boko Haram is fighting in the north east, bandits in the north west and Fulani militants in the north central which in turn makes such spaces more prone to terrorist recruitment. Although ungoverned spaces were hypothetically not

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an ungoverned environment, but were being controlled in a different manner than formal states. These were areas where there was a fractional government presence or were poorly governed by the existing formal authorities which posed security risks to the state (Keister, J. 2014). Terrorism, criminal activities, drug trafficking and the likes are the by-products of ungoverned spaces (Chloe, D. 2011). According to the RAND report, examples of ungoverned spaces with possibilities of accommodating terrorist organizations were drawn from eight regions, including the East African Corridor, West Africa, the Sulawesi–Mindanao Arc, the Colombia–Venezuela Border, the Guatemala–Chiapas Border, the Pakistan–Afghanistan Border, the North Caucasus and the Arabian Peninsula. In this study, RAND examined ungoverned spaces through two magnitudes: conduciveness to terrorism and ungovernability (A. Rabasa and J.E. Peters, 2007)

Armed Conflict-An armed conflict exists whenever there is a resort to armed force between States or protracted armed violence between governmental authorities and organized armed groups or between such groups within a state.”(www.yorku.ca: 2024). Armed conflict can also be defined as ‘‘a political conflict in which armed combat involves the armed forces of at least one state (or one or more armed factions seeking to gain control of all or part of the state), and in which at least 1,000 people have been killed by the fighting during the course of the conflict.”(www.ploughshares.ca: 2024). Armed factions such as the bandits, kidnappers, cattle rustlers and other non-state actors have taken over the northwest running riots and killing hundreds of human beings without any regard to International Humanitarian Law. The civilians are not protected in the conflict as this poses a complex challenge to the Nigerian military. The Military have been found wanting in ensuring the safety and well-being of the citizens that constantly come under the attacks of these armed criminals. In a lecture delivered by Professor Zulum, the Borno State Governor during the 60th anniversary of the Nigerian Defence Academy; he said’’ the deliberate targeting of civilians, indiscriminate attacks, and the use of tactics that cause excessive harm to non-combatants persist, leading to devastating consequences for civilian populations (www.vanguard.com; 2024). The bandits have used tactics such as burning of villages, looting, raping, killing and forceful tax collection from the farmers to suppress and intimidate non-combatant civilians. The people in the region have been ravaged by the armed conflicts According to a report in one of the states in the region, between 2011 and 2019; bandits killed at least 6,319 people, kidnapped 3,672 people and destroyed more than 500 villages. (This Day; 2019).

Kinetic Approach- This is a Military practice of deploying conventional ordnance and explosives to engage and inflict destructive physical damage upon opposition resources, assets, and forces. In other words, Kinetic military action is a military action involving active warfare, including lethal force. The kinetic approach involves aggressive and offensive measures to eliminate or capture network members and their supporters. Lethal measures have been applied to fight the criminal armed groups in the northwest that is holding the region in the jugular. Combined military operations as well as Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF), have all been launched against the armed groups waging war in the northwest of Nigeria.

Non-Kinetic-Non-kinetic warfare generally refers to action against an adversary without a direct conventional military action. It comprises possibilities such as information warfare, cyber warfare, psychological operations, electromagnetic offensives and cryptographic warfare. The non-kinetic approach involves the use of subtle, non-coercive means for combating dark networks. Little or none of the unconventional military approach to address the armed conflict in the northwest has not been seen and this probably explains why the conflict is still raging. The military campaigns to quell the armed conflict in the region are not producing the desired result.

Peace-Definitions from Oxford Dictionary for peace are freedom from disturbance, tranquillity; a state or period in which there is no war or a war has ended. Nigeria is in a state of non-declared war with the non-state actors (NSA), waging war constantly against the state. The northwest has come under the attacks of the bandits and other armed groups for the past ten years. There is hardly a week that there won't be any case of cattle rustling, bandits attacks or kidnapping in the region. As a result of incessant attacks of the armed men, farmers could no longer go to their farms or harvest their farm produce because of the fear of being killed or kidnapped for ransom by the gun men. In the last ten years, there is no peace in the northwest as armed men are busy killing, kidnapping people and destroying villages and farm lands.

THEORETICAL DISCOURSE

The theoretical discourse of this work is explained within the context of ‘poverty and socio-economic marginalization’. When a sizeable young population is neglected in the society and deprived of economic benefits for so long to the extent that they become poor; the resultant effect is violence in which the deprived young people take up arms against the state to demand for their own share of the ‘national cake’. Violence manifestations such as insurgency, banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling etc. have their roots in poverty and socio-economic injustices that the perpetrators of these heinous crimes have suffered in the past and without any hope of being addressed by the government. In a research project that was sponsored by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) aimed at tracing the root causes of extremism in Africa, where more than 350 apprehended extremists were

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interviewed from Nigeria, Uganda, Somalia, Niger, Cameroon and Kenya; they all claimed that they were not influenced by religious doctrines. They were rather enthused by the long experience of deprivation, they claimed that they were not subject to a government’s positive contribution to help their state of poverty nor did they experience a basic provision from the state, with respect to secular education or health (UNDP; 2017). Poverty, unemployment, lack of basic social amenities and absence of economic power, have contributed to the on-going armed conflict in northwest Nigeria.

According to Schatz & Schiffer (2008), socio-economic marginalization could be defined as a process by which people or group is denied accessing relevant positions and authorities in terms of economic, social, political and religious benefits in the community or society. Usually, a marginal group has numerical strength in terms of number compared to the minority group that is in possession of the economic and political power in the society. Socio-economic marginalization explains the position of individual member of the community, groups or population in contrast with main stream members of society. To be marginalized is to be distanced from contributing to the society and isolated from social, economic and political benefits inherent in the society or community. People who are marginalized in the society or community have poor access to social and economic benefits such as education, employment, health care/medical services, housing opportunities, politics and governance, social services and the likes. This situation makes marginalized citizens to be distanced from political power and economic resources which ordinarily drives self-determination. Hence, their participation and self-determination in the community or society is usually low (Whitehead & Dahigren, 2006). According to Birchall (2019), socio-economic marginalization is the economic, social and political exclusion of people or individuals in society such that the individual or groups are unable to participate fully in the economy of the society. Usually, people who are socially and economically excluded are women, girls, physically challenged individuals, ethnic/religious minority, children and youth, migrants and internally displaced individuals, people with terminal sicknesses such as HIV as well as cancer patients just to mention but a few (Birchall, 2019). The leadership in any society that fails to ensure equal treatment is given to all citizens irrespective of ethnic, class, age, educational background, career, sexual orientation etc. engender violence such as we see it on-going in northwest of Nigeria. Socio-economic marginalization instituted by the leadership of a society or community can leave some section of the society aggrieved, which may lead to tension, agitations and restiveness and this will ultimately impact negatively on community development. Thus, Birchall (2019), study which employed qualitative research design and the findings of the study which states that social exclusion negatively impact the development of the Nigerian society and indeed, several empirical scholar works are in agreement with this theoretical discourse. The leadership that manages the affairs of the people and the resources should ensure that no form of discrimination or marginalization is melted on any section of the society in order to maintain peace.

On theoretical discourse of poverty, there are three major factors of poverty: The individual factors that fuel poverty such as attitude, human capital and welfare participation (Gans, 1995). The second factor is Cultural and Neighbourhood Factors. This explains how poverty is created and maintained in some neighbourhoods or among some groups. The cultural and neighbourhood factors relate to the influence of people’s residential environment that tends to shape poverty or success. The third factor is Structural Factors. Larger economic and social structures have been found to account for poverty. Perspectives regarding structural factors argue that capitalism creates conditions that promote poverty. Beeghley (2000) noted the effect of economic structure stating that irrespective of individual effort (hard work, skill); the structure of the United States economy ensures that millions of people are poor. Specifically, the Davis and Moores’ functionalist theory, labour market theories, and the social exclusion perspective threw more light on the structural causes of poverty. The functionalist theory of social stratification argues that poverty is an important social, economic and political function for society in general, and for the middle and Wealthy classes in particular (Davis & Moores, 1945). On the basis of labour wages, functionalist theory accounts for the causes of poverty among certain people and groups in society. In their thesis, Davis and Moore emphasized the functional importance of some category of skills and knowledge in society. According to Davis and Moore, there are certain positions and functions in society that need special skills and knowledge for effective handling. They argued that conversion of one’s talent into skills and knowledge requires a training period during which the individuals undergoing such training must sacrifice in some manner. Davis and Moore suggested that people should be motivated with higher wages and privileges to undergo this sacrifice and training, otherwise society will suffer. Higher percentage of the people in the northwest is unemployed let alone being motivated with higher wages and privileges of training, thus, the society in the region is suffering from armed violent conflict for years and it seems there is no solution to end the conflict.

To further explain poverty as one of the major causes of armed conflict in the northwest of Nigeria; the definition and measurement of poverty gives an understanding of poverty in the region. Kotler, Roberto, & Leisner, (2006), underscored three main approaches to poverty definition and measurement. The first is Monetary Poverty. According to Laderchi et al. (2003), the monetary approach defines poverty in terms of how much a person’s income (or consumption) falls short of some minimum level of resources. Second is Capability Poverty. Capability poverty is the failure of a person to achieve basic capabilities to adequately fulfil certain crucial functions at minimal level (Saith, 2001; Sen, 1985). The capability approach views monetary resource as

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means that can help to enhance people’s well-being. The final one is called Social Exclusion Poverty. Social exclusion is a situation whereby an individual is denied the opportunity to participate in the normal activities of citizens whether he desires to participate or not. As a relational process, social exclusion theory view poverty as a declining participation and access to resources. Laderchi et al. (2003) outlined the attributes of social exclusion: multidimensionality, dynamic, relational, active, relative and contextual. The multidimensionality of social exclusion refers to idea that the experience of exclusion exists in economic, social, and political forms. Olson (as cited in Jordan, 1996) noted that people become vulnerable to poverty when they are excluded from a rent-seeking organized group within a market economy. He argued that poverty caused by mass unemployment in the 1970s was created by the collective action of special interest groups that marginalized others in the labour market. Furthermore, social exclusion occurs when a person or group is deprived of its social status. Usually, individuals or groups are denied all of their social existence within mainstream society. When social exclusion occurs the individuals affected do not have an equal opportunity for jobs in the labour market (Bessis, 1995). In the political arena, social exclusion occurs when a certain groups including women and racial and religious minorities are deprived of part or all of their political rights. The multidimensional aspect of social exclusion also emphasizes to the causal connection between the different dimensions of exclusion. The citizens behind the banditry and kidnapping in the northwest economically, socially and politically excluded which denied them of equal opportunity in the society. The denial of equal opportunity in the society has turned to armed conflict in the northwest in which the people of the region mostly bear the brunt of violent conflict. Poverty rather than political, ethnic, ideology or sectional interest, is responsible for the armed conflict in the northwest. Poverty drives extortion, ransom and other criminal funds which regularly lubricates the wheel of armed violence in the region.

BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEMS

Since the advent of democracy in Nigeria in 2009, Nigeria has been facing security challenges in form of terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, Killer herdsmen attacks, armed robbery, oil pipeline vandalism etc. all of which have heightened insecurity in different parts of the country. Due to these security issues, many Nigerians have criticized the government and called for total overhauling of the security apparatus for an improved internal security. In addressing the growing security issues in the country, sub-national government have even created regional security outfits such as the Amotekun in the South West; the Shege Kafasa, formed by the Coalition of Northern Group (CNG); while the South East formed Ebube Agu security outfit. Different regional security outfits were formed in response to different security threats in the country that has claimed many lives, polarised communities, bartered the economy, increased poverty and created fears in the hearts of the citizens. The northern Nigeria used to be peaceful as the rate of ordinary crime was much lower in the 1970s, and began to grow in the 1980s. Mahmud Jega, put in context the nature of problems facing the North during that time. In his article titled ‘Fire from Borno to Sokoto’ he said what was prevalent at that time were violent political contests during the First Republic, including the Tiv riots; frequent inter-communal clashes, among the worst being the Kafanchan riots of 1987; and the violent Maitatsine religious sect that first struck at Yan Awaki, Kano in 1980 and later at Bulunkutu, Maiduguri; Tudun Wada, Kaduna; Yola, Gombe and finally in Funtua in 1993 (www.dailytrust.com.ng: 2020). During that period, there was no kidnapping for ransom while banditry was not rampant as it is today while the Forests were not being used for criminal activities. Currently the Forests in the region have become a safe haven for bandits and kidnapers where they plan and lunch attacks on the villagers, kill people, rustle animals, sexually abuse young girls and women or kidnap people for ransom. The vast forests and unfriendly terrains in the north west of the country are veritable instrument in the hand of the bandits to commit atrocities. Due to the unfriendly and inaccessible terrains, bandits have been operating unchecked in Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, Kaduna and Kebbi with high magnitude of fatalities and creating huge humanitarian crisis. According to a report published by ACAPS, (project of Norwegian Refugee Council, Mercy Corps and Save The Children), a non-profit organization; stated that more than 1,100 people were killed in 2018 in the six states of the region, over 2,200 were killed in 2019, and more than 1,600 fatalities were recorded between January – June 2020 (Council on Foreign Relations: 2020). By September 2019, such attacks had internally displaced over 160,000 people and produced more than 41,000 refugees (WFP: 2019; UNHCR: 2019). Since 2016, almost daily attacks by bandits have been recorded in Zamfara, Katsina, and Sokoto prompting the Nigeria government to institute various security operations in the northwest. There are risks of getting kidnapped specifically for ransom (BBC: 2020). The northwest has come under a siege of armed men killing and maiming people with wanton destruction of properties. The identified swaths ‘ungoverned spaces’ in the region which criminal elements are using to carry out their heinous crimes include: the Rugu Forest in Katsina State; Kuduru, Rijaria & Akibu Forests, Kaduna State; Fagore Forest, Kano State; Gold reserves in Sokoto and Zamfara States. The inability of the military and security agencies to wipe out the bandits, kidnapers, gun men and other criminal elements in the northwest of Nigeria is largely due to ‘ungoverned spaces’ which have been serving as protection for the criminals.

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THE LINKAGE BETWEEN ‘UNGOVERNED SPACES’ AND ARMED CONFLICT IN NIGERIA

There is strong linkage between ‘ungoverned spaces’ and armed conflict in Nigeria in the sense that they are inter-related. ‘Ungoverned spaces’ are safe haven for the armed men; they are sanctuaries for the criminals and their weapons. It is important to note that “different ungoverned spaces” exemplify “different threats” (Patrick, S. 2007). The threats of ‘ungoverned spaces’ in the third world countries are different from that of the developed world. Some criminal activities that have been carried out in the Western World have occurred in a well-governed area and not in their ungoverned spaces; while poorly governed areas have been ‘colonized’ by the criminals engaging in armed conflict against the citizens in both rural and urban spaces. As rightly noted that ungoverned spaces are areas where the state institutions cannot exercise their full authority (R. Olaniyan and R. T. Akinyele; 2016). Forests and caves in the northwest Nigeria are serving as sanctuaries for the kidnapers, bandits and cattle rustlers in the region. For example, the Rugu Forest which spans over 220 km, borders the four states of Katsina, Zamfara, and Kaduna, and extends to the state of Niger in the north central and neighbouring border communities of the Republic of Niger (www.researchgate.net; 2024). Bandits and kidnapers’ operations are linked to ‘ungoverned spaces’. For instance, the activities of bandits and kidnapers are carried out in unguarded Rugu forest where the abductees are detained, ransom demanded and paid. The bandits have left behind colossal destruction in Kajuru, Birni Guari in Kaduna State, the seven Local Government Areas that Rugu Forest cut across in Katsina State (Jibia, Safana, Batsari, Danmusa, Sabuwa, Dandume, Faskari); and spans over Kuta/Shiroro LGA in Niger State. The ‘ungoverned spaces’ has the capability to trigger armed conflicts. In Iraq for example, the Hamrin mountain range, that spreads along Salah al-Din, Diyala and Kirkuk provinces were captured by the Islamic State (IS) to promote its recalcitrant attacks. The lack of governance in this area allowed the IS to carry out their lethal operations at night, especially when all security forces had returned to their bases. Furthermore, the IS was able to finance its operation through robberies, kidnappings for ransom, extortions and carjacking (O’Driscoll; 2019). The present-day Federation of Northern Syria Rojava, Mali and Somaliland have demonstrated how ‘ungoverned spaces’ are able to pose as an enormous threat to international security (Lloyd, R.B. 2016). The ‘ungoverned spaces’ of Gold mining sites in Zamfara and Sokoto States, and the Rugu Forests that traverse Katsina, Kaduna and Niger States in Nigeria; have motivated and encouraged armed conflicts in the northwest resulting in deaths and wanton destruction of properties. ‘Ungoverned spaces’ therefore bring threats, instability and insecurity to its host government thereby challenging the state capabilities to deal with the armed groups roving the rural and urban centres. There are numerous factors that encourage criminal or terrorist organizations to dwell in ‘ungoverned spaces’, these include the inability of the government to penetrate the area; absence of government authorities; lack of physical infrastructure; and inability of the government to exercise a monopoly of force (Foreign and Commonwealth Office, 2014). All these have aided criminals to freely operate in the northwest and continue to grow their evil acts.

APPROACHES TO RESOLVE THE ARMED CONFLICT IN THE NORTHWEST NIGERIA.

There are two broad approaches identified to tackle the armed conflict in the region: kinetic and non-kinetic. The first has been copiously deployed while the later remain largely untapped to solve the problem of armed violence in the northwest Nigeria.

THE KINETIC APPROACH

Varied joint security operations were instituted in the northwest in tackling the growing insecurity in the region. These included the Nigerian Military Operation Sharan Daji; Operation Puff Adder; the Nigerian Army, Air Force, Counter Terrorism Unit (CTU); Police Mobile Force, Nigerian Police, Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF); and Local Vigilantes; have all been deployed to silence armed men in the North West, but to no avail. Despite ceaseless airstrikes from Nigerian Air force, jets on the bandits hideouts and positions, “The invincible Rugu Forest Daemons’ re-appear and become more deadly and brutish. The bandits have turned the northwest states of Zamfara, Sokoto and Katsina into killing Fields, Ransom-bug and Cattle Rustling territory. Several military campaigns have been launched against the bandits in the region. For example, the Nigerian Air Force (NAF) Air Task Force (ATF) of Operation DIRAN MIKIYA, neutralised several bandits at a compound in Rugu Forest in Zamfara, in the first week of February 2019. According to NAF Director of Public Relations and Information, Air Commodore Ibikunle Daramola, said, intelligence reports led to the identification of several camps being used by the bandits to launch attacks against innocent civilians. He stated” One of the air interdiction missions was conducted at dawn at a location in Rugu Forest South of Gurbin Baure, where some armed bandits were seen assembled by a logistics truck parked near their compound-hideout”(www.faapa.info; 2019). Apart from the efforts of the Federal Government of Nigeria to address the insecurity in the northwest of Nigeria; the State Governors of the region also came together on Wednesday 31 January 2024, pledged to work together and adopt a common approach in tackling armed conflict and security challenges bedevilling the region. The Katsina State Governor, one of the front line states experiencing banditry, in his statement during the inauguration of the Zamfara State Community Protection Guard (ZSCPG), he said effective synergy and the adoption of common approach by the state will go a long way towards addressing insecurity and foster relative peace in the region. He stated that ‘we have agreed to commit

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ourselves in fighting banditry and other crimes, and say no to negotiations with any criminal, but those surrendered and embrace peace would be integrated into the community” (www.vanguardngr.com; 2024). This is another kinetic approach which has not brought solution to banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling and other criminal activities that have engulfed the region in the past ten years. State or regional security outfits have not resolved the armed conflict in the northwest where the military as well as Vigilante Groups have been deployed to bring peace in the trouble region. Bandits that were granted amnesty by the previous regime and the so called repentant bandits have all gone back to their trade of killing and ransom taking and the cycle of violence continues.

THE NON-KINETIC APPROACHES

The kinetic approach in addressing the armed conflict in the northwest has been assessed and discovered that it has not transformed the armed conflict in the region. The following non-kinetic approaches have been identified to put an end to the intractable armed violence in the northwest Nigeria.

Real-time intelligence:-The ability to collect high value intelligence in near real-time and correctly interpret the intelligence will provide good advantage to win the armed groups in the northwest. Human intelligence reports will provide the lead to the hide out and operational bases of the criminals in the area. People have argued that the Federal Government is not making use of intelligence gathering and clamoured that intelligence should be deplored which will help the military in their real combat to win the armed conflict in the region. The people in the affected communities know the criminals among them that are engaging in the illicit business of kidnapping, cattle rustling and other criminalities in their domains and it will not be difficult to give information if the government can be sincere and ensure the safety of the informants. In many cases, informants are identified by the kidnapers and are being killed by the kidnapers. Lack of safety will not encourage the people to give information on the criminals in the community. The government must build trust in the people for intelligent to be fruitful.

Unmanned Drones for surveillance to monitor the forests:-The laws in Nigeria forbid states or individuals to acquire drones in Nigeria. These laws have not helped in resolving armed conflict in the country. The armed groups are hiding in the forests and mountains making them invisible by the military to deal with them decisively. Unmanned Smart Nano drones can be deployed to get the exact locations of the criminal gangs marauding and terrorising the region. The size and terrains of some of the forests where the criminals operate and use as safe haven are difficult for the military to navigate or keep surveillance to apprehend the armed bandits that are using the forests as sanctuaries. Drones will help the military to get the precise location, the size of the camps, weapons at the disposal of the bandits and criminals that have invaded the forests and wreaking havoc in the communities.

The use of technology: - The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Cyber warfare are strategies to win the on-going armed conflict in the northwest. The conventional warfare is not yielding the result of winning the war against the armed groups in the region. Many times, the Nigeria Soldiers have been ambushed, killed and their weapons taken away by the bandits in the region. Artificial Intelligence and Cyber war against the armed groups will neutralise the illicit weapons they have acquired and make them more vulnerable to the law enforcement agents. Artificial Intelligence could also be used to collect data on criminals occupying the forests in the northwest as it has the capacity to increase mass surveillance.

Conscious rapid Infrastructural development of the region; - It has been canvassed in many quarters that the reason for the growing insecurity in the northwest is linked to the underdevelopment of the region by both state and Federal Government of Nigeria. Public analysts, commentators and scholars have argued that the neglected growing population that have no education or trade and unemployed young people are now in arm against the state to demand for their own fair share of the resources, resulting in banditry and kidnapping of the citizenry irrespective of the ethnic or religious background of their victims. Lack of infrastructural development such as electricity, good road network, water supply and irrigation for farming, medical facilities, recreational facilities etc. are fuelling armed conflict in the region. There is a nexus between infrastructures and economic development. Evidently, there is a high correlation between availability of infrastructural services and the income levels of most economies. Studies have been conducted which indicate that the impact of infrastructure on growth and development is substantial and significant. Indeed, it has been established that the impact of infrastructure investment on development is much higher than the impact of the investment in other forms of capital (www.cbn.gov.ng; 2024). When there are functional infrastructures, the economic development will be stimulated and the people will be economically empowered to earn a living instead of taking into criminalities. The state of infrastructures in the region is very bad. Many areas are not covered with electricity, telecommunication while access roads are not available and sizable number of population is cut off from modernity.

Improved governance in the Region: - Governance in this sense is the act or process of governing or overseeing the control and direction of the state affairs in a way that is more beneficial to the people. There is a high degree of loss of faith in government and governance, and loss of face to the Nigerian state due to governance failure over the years. Good governance that will address the ills of the society is very germane in addressing the on-going armed conflict in the region. Many Local Government Areas are farther apart to each other and without any security apparatus in place while in some cases; the Courts of law to try criminals are

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non-existence. In some cases, one Commercial Bank serves 7-8 Local Government Areas. Many Local Government Areas merely exist by name but lacks administrative and fiscal power as they are being controlled by the state governments. A more responsive system of governance is required to stem the tide of violence in the region. Good governance entails proper functioning of government institutions irrespective of the government in power. The major problem of the region is lack of good governance. A situation whereby the state authority could not exercise its political authority and use its institutional resources to manage problems and the affairs of the society to carry out its fundamental duty of protecting life and property of her citizens; lacks the ingredients of good governance. Good governance's characteristics include: Participation, Rule of law, Transparency, Responsiveness, Consensus oriented, Equity and inclusiveness, Effectiveness and efficiency, Accountability (www.uclg-aspac.org; 2021). When these characteristics of good governance are juxtaposed with the situation in the Northwest; one can quickly conclude that there is no good governance in the region and this is what is exacerbating armed violence in the area.

Poverty and unemployment Reduction: - The prolonged application of brute force or kinetic warfare over the years has not solved the problem and one of the root causes of insecurity in the northwest is poverty and unemployment. The rural poor are far bigger than urban population in which vast majority are unemployed. Poverty and unemployment can make someone to take into crimes in order to survive. An average human being needs basic things of life-food, shelter, clothes. When a man cannot afford these, he is being pushed into crime to get those basic things at all cost. Poverty reduces human dignity. The states in the region and Federal government should reduce poverty if not totally eradicate it and develop a master plan for industrialization that will employ hundreds of thousands of the youths in the northwest of Nigeria. It is imperative to solve rural poverty problem for the sustenance of peace. To solve poverty problems in the rural areas where the bandits and kidnappers hold sway; the Food and Agriculture Organization, (FAO), identified the following: increasing productivity of small-scale farms and improve their access to markets, promoting more efficient value chains, creating jobs, especially for the youth, encouraging economic diversification and, investing in people and fostering skills that can be used in agricultural and non-agricultural activities (www.fao.org; 2024). When poverty is reduced to its barest minimum, peace and development will blossom because, there is a direct link between poverty and violence as discussed above.

Youth empowerment:-Youth empowerment is a veritable instrument to address the grievances of the young people and make them part of process that will fast track development and engender sustainable peace in the northwest. The youth should be empowered economically and educationally in order to play a meaningful role in bringing to an end the armed conflict ravaging the region. When the youth are empowered economically and educational wise, there is likelihood of them not engaging in kidnapping or cattle rustling which are largely driven by the desire to make money. Violence and criminality are thriving in the rural areas of the region and the causes are not farfetched. Arisukwu and Asaju, identified salient causes of this which are: youth unemployment, poverty, hunger, poor health and living conditions and ethno-religious challenges are responsible for violence and disenchantment within the rural areas (Arisukwu, 2017; Arisukwu et al., 2019, 2020; Asaju et al., 2014). When the young people are gainfully employed and empowered economically; there won't be room for them to engage in violent act in their community.

Improved and Re-vitalise Rural Economy; - The economy of many community has been destroyed due to the activities of the bandits and kidnappers and new business of becoming an informant to the kidnappers for monetary gain has surfaced and well maintained by the criminals. When there is enabling environment for economic growth and the citizens are able to engage in one legitimate job or the other; those informants to the criminals desist from the illicit venture and opt for legitimate jobs. The rural economy has the capacity to absorb hundreds of the jobless youth if priority is given to its revitalization by the states in the region. Small businesses should be encouraged and loan facilities should be provided at the rural levels to stimulate rural economy. Financial scheme that gives rural people access to credit or savings, or a process that supports rural businesses, such as training programme or a rural enterprise support center; will automatically improve rural business which will reduce criminality as the citizenries engage in one form of business or the other. Another strategy to foster rural economy is by fostering rural-urban linkages, promoting cooperative efforts, investing in infrastructure, and providing rural areas with access to markets, technology, and education. The government should sponsor agricultural education to promote modern farming, support rural infrastructures such as provision of internet services and, promote local farm products by buying locally made farm products. This will contribute to sustainable rural development and improved rural economy. Re-vitalization of rural economy will help to end banditry in the northwest Nigeria. In an interview conducted by Taylor & Francis online, published online by African Security Review; posits that banditry developed and intensified as a result of a governance deficit, a significant disparity in wealth distribution, and a disconnection between the government and the people. Additionally, the issues of unemployment, the growing problem of population boom in Nigeria's northwest, and the strain of poverty contribute to this phenomenon. The following interview confirms these assertions.

... We were seriously facing economic difficulties because there were no jobs apart from hard labour on the farm. You could be hired to work on the farm for the whole day for just ₦1000 [\$1.4 USD] or even less. It was not enough to live on less than ₦1000 a day and that could only be gotten after 12 hours work on farm. It was because of that extreme poverty that we formed our own

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bandit group and started attacking people. Our group developed and became one of the most dangerous bandits groups in the whole of Birnin Gwari LGA. We did all the atrocities on the people. We abducted many children and their mothers and collected millions of naira as ransom in the 7 years I took as bandit (www.tandonline.com; 2024). So, therefore, disparities in wealth distribution and strain of poverty have contributed hugely to banditry in the northwest of Nigeria. The Government should endeavour to embark on wealth creation through economic re-vitalization programme in order to close the existing wide gap in wealth distribution in the region.

Education; - The majority of the young people that are engaged in kidnapping and banditry are uneducated, making them to be cruel and barbaric in their disposition. Life means nothing to them because they don't understand what it means for one to invest in his/her own life. Education liberates the mind and empowers for greatness. The literacy level in the region is very low and this account for a high level of ignorance in which the uneducated mass people can be easily lured into crimes and criminalities. The recruitment of the ignorant folks is very easy as little money can get them to take arms against their human fellow and the state. According to the Katsina State Governor, Dikko Umar Radda, he said recruitment into banditry has been found to be the major problem of criminality in the northwest that the entire region must tackle. Massive education programmes that will encourage the school age pupils to go to school must be embarked upon in order to curtail or cut off the recruitment of the young people into carrying arms. No doubt that banditry has affected education in the region. Many schools have been attacked and students kidnapped for ransom. Incessant school attacks by the bandits have increased the number of drop outs and out-of-school children in the region. Generally, the North West has suffered low enrolment rates due to the prevalence in the region of Islamic education, because most parents are yet to embrace Western education. Only 61% of 6-11 year-olds attend primary school regularly, while only 35.6% of 3-5 year-olds receive early childhood education (www.premiumtimesng.com; 2024). Various reasons, including economic hurdles and sociocultural norms and practices, contribute to education deprivation in northern Nigeria and discourage participation in formal school, especially for girls. Female primary school net attendance rates in the North East and North West regions are 47.7% and 47.3%, respectively, implying that more than half of the overall population of girls are not in school (National Population Commission (Nigeria) and RTI International; 2015). From the foregoing, the level of education in the Northwest has been generally poor even before the upsurge of attacks on schools. Therefore, the government, as matter of necessity, make concerted effort to improve the education from primary to tertiary in the region. Both the State and Federal Government have to partner together and upscale educational development in the northwest of the country in order to reduce the impact of banditry attacks on schools and also increase the school enrolment. Bursaries and other incentives to encourage young people to go to school should be introduced at all level of education in the region.

Back Channel Diplomacy to address injustices & grievances: Until and unless the concerns of certain individuals that are involved in the conflict are addressed, achieving a lasting peace in the northwest might be a mirage. The armed conflict in the region is sustained as a result of revenge due to heinous crime committed against them. The scars and bitterness of the past injuries against certain individuals have made them to take into banditry and would not relent until the government at the national and sub-national level take concrete steps to address injustices and grievances of the people. Excerpt of an interview conducted by Taylor and Francis online with a prominent bandit leader elucidate this point.

... For over 40 years, Fulani people are being attacked by other people and the government has never been serious about ending the senseless attacks on the Fulani all over the country. This is the reason many of us have taken up arms in order to defend ourselves. I am about 42 years now. This thing has been happening long before I was born ... We will take revenge for all the killings and destruction Fulanis have experienced. Let them prepare for 100 years of killing, torturing, kidnapping and terror. Our children will continue where we stop. That is exactly what our attackers have done against us (www.tandonline.com; 2024).

The Fulanis are not the only tribe that has suffered some degree of injustice in the region. The Hausas and other minority tribes have been gruesomely murdered and are crying for justice. Non Fulanis felt that the Fulanis are over protected by the state and enjoy certain privileges and benefits at the expense of other tribes. This in itself leads to grievances.

Another perspective on the issue of addressing injustice and grievances is buttressed with the below episode.

I joined banditry through my friend whose father was butchered by people believed to be farmers. Few days before his death some of his cattle transgressed to a nearby farm as he was grazing his animals. The animals destroyed very few crops. My friend's father demanded that the damage should be quantified in monetary value so that he would pay. The owner said he didn't want compensation but rather would take action he deemed fit. One morning as he was grazing his animals in the bush, the farmer and his friend attacked the man and cut off his neck vein with a knife. Since then my friend and his siblings vowed to take the worst retaliation against the entire farming community here in Gundumi and Kamarawa communities in Isa. One of his children was my friend and he invited [me] to help him fulfil his vows. This case is one out of thousands. Similar incidents have happened to so many of us (www.tandonline.com; 2024).

There are several cases of grievances caused by banditry in the northwest Nigeria. Bandits have killed mothers, fathers, and children. In some cases, they go to the Mosques and Churches, shoot randomly during worship; storm villages during market days

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and kill as many as they can. All these are generating animosity and grievances against the state that has failed to protect them and if opportunity avails to revenge or retaliate, the victims will do so and the cycle of violence will continue unabated.

COMBINATION OF THE TWO APPROACHES IN RESOLVING THE ARMED CONFLICT?

The position of this paper is to advocate for more non-kinetic measures as it has shown clearly that a single approach of kinetic method has not been able to resolve the conflict in the northwest of Nigeria. Despite the various military interventions/strategies, the armed violence is still on-going with varying degree of human misery caused by the armed men in the region. However, it is strongly believe that the combination of kinetic and more of non-kinetic strategies will possibly resolve the armed conflict in the region. Non-kinetic is not a sign of weakness to the military but to complement the military efforts in bringing peace to the region. Peace is what is needed in the region and if non-kinetic methods as discussed above will bring a lasting peace in the region; it will be of interest to the generality of the people in the area and indeed, the entire country to utilize the strategies.

SUGGESTION AND WAY FORWARD

The former Chief of Defence Staff, Major-General Lucky Irabor (rtd), announced and endorsed the purported change of strategy in ending the armed conflict in the country. Also, the former President, Muhammadu Buhari, advocated for a change in strategy in the fight against the bandits, terrorists and kidnapers in the country. The current President, Bola Tinubu, and the present military brass also lend their voices to the change of strategy. The Nigerian government has been speaking of a change of strategy to non-kinetic warfare for upwards of five years. The government must move beyond the words and work the talk by designing a follow-up action in adopting non-kinetic approaches discussed above and others identified measures to end armed conflict ravaging the northwest region. The non-kinetic approaches discussed above should be carried out in the entire northwest states simultaneously for effectiveness purpose because; as the programme is being carried out in one state and other states are left behind, armed group in the contiguous states might sabotage the programme. The non-kinetic approaches should be carried out at both regional and Federal levels in the region for maximum impact.

CONCLUSION

Nigerian Government has deployed kinetic instruments in fighting insurgency/terrorism for the past sixteen years most especially in the North West of Nigeria. The insecurity milieu has spread to the North West, North Central and gradually spill-over to the South West of the country in which bandits, kidnapers, killer Herdsmen and unknown gunmen running riots killing and kidnapping innocent citizens. In order to tame this evil tide, it is imperative for the Federal Government that is constitutionally empowered to protect life and properties of the citizenries, to look inward and combine subtle diplomacy of non-kinetic approaches discussed above with the on-going kinetic measures to end the armed conflict and incessant killings and misery in the country.

REFERENCES

- 1) Rabasa and J.E. Peters, (2007) “Dimensions of Ungovernability,” in *Ungoverned territories: Understanding and reducing terrorism risks*, ed. A. Rabasa, S. Boraz, P. Chalk, K. Cragin, & T. W. Karasik (Rand Corporation, California, USA, 2007).
- 2) Taylor, (2016): 6 A. J. Taylor, “Thoughts on the Nature and Consequences of Ungoverned Spaces,” *SAIS Review of International Affairs* 36, no.1 (2016): 5–15.
- 3) Arisukwu, (2017); Arisukwu et al., 2019, 2020; Asaju et al., 2014). *Causes of Crime in Rural Areas*
- 4) BBC: 2023. Obtained 8 August 2023
- 5) Beeghley, L. (2000). *The Structure of social stratification in the United States*. New York, NY: Pearson.
- 6) Bessis, S. (1995). *From social exclusion to social cohesion: Towards a policy agenda*.
- 7) Birchall, J. (2019). *Overview of social exclusion in Nigeria*. K4D Helpdesk report. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development studies.
- 8) Chloe Diggins, (2011) “Ungoverned Space, Fragile States, and Global Threats: Deconstructing Linkages,” *Inquiries Journal* 3, no. 03 (2011).
- 9) Council on Foreign Relations: Obtained 12 October 2023
- 10) Daily Trust; 2019).
- 11) Davis, K. & Moore, W. (1945). *Some principle of stratification*. *American Sociological Review*, 10 (2), 242-249.
- 12) Foreign and Commonwealth Office, (2014). *The link between “ungoverned spaces” and terrorism: myth or reality?* August, 2014.
- 13) Gans, H. (1995). *The war against the poor*. New York, NY: Basic Book.

The ‘Ungoverned Spaces’ and Armed Conflict in the North West Nigeria: Kinetic or Non-Kinetic Approach to Attain Peace in the Region?

- 14) J. Keister, (2014) “The Illusion of Chaos: Why Ungoverned Spaces Aren’t Ungoverned, and Why that Matters,” Cato Institute Policy Analysis, no. 766 (2014).
- 15) Jordan, B. (1996). A theory of poverty and social exclusion. Cambridge, MA: Polity Press. Kaufman P., Alt M., & Chapman C. (2000). Dropout rates in the United States. Obtained from <http://nces.ed.gov>. 16 March 2024
- 16) Key Informant Interview (2023) with a former bandit in Sabon Layi, Birnin-Gwari Local Government Area of Kaduna State on July 9, 2023. Obtained 20 April 2024
- 17) Key Informant Interview (2023) with a battlefield bandit in in Gundumi, Isa Local Government Area of Sokoto State on July 18, 2023. Obtained on 18 April 2024.
- 18) Key Informant Interview (2023) with a battlefield in Gundumi, Isa Local Government Area, Sokoto State on July 18, 2023. Obtained on 18 April 2024.
- 19) Kotler, P., Roberto, N., & Leisner, T. (2006). Alleviating poverty: A macro/micro marketing perspective, *Journal of Macromarketing*, 26 (3), 233-238.
- 20) Laderchi, C., Saith, R. & Stewart, F. (2003). Does it matter that we do not agree on the definition of poverty: A comparison of four approaches. *Oxford Development Studies*, 31 (3), 233-274.
- 21) Lloyd, R.B. (2016) “Ungoverned Spaces and Regional Insecurity: The Case of Mali,” *SAIS Review of International Affairs* 36, no. 1 (2016): 133–41.
- 22) National Population Commission (Nigeria) and RTI International, “Nigeria Education Data Survey (NEDS)”, Washington, DC, US Agency for International Development, 2015.
- 23) O’Driscoll, (2019); *Governing the “ungoverned”: Suppressing the Islamic State’s insurgency in Iraq*. Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (2019).
- 24) Patrick, S. (2007) “Failed States and Global Security: Empirical Questions and Policy Dilemmas,” *International Studies Review* 9, no. 4 (2007): 644–62
- 25) Premium Times, “39% of Children in North-west Except Kaduna, Are out of School – UNICEF”, 27 August 2019, <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/regional/nwest/348897-39-ofchildren-in-north-west>. Obtained 20 April 2024
- 26) Prosecutor v. Dusko Tadic, No. IT-94-1-AR 72, International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia Appeals Chamber in International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2011). *Glossary of Migration*, 2nd Edition. Obtained 9 February 2024
- 27) R. Olaniyan and R. T. Akinyele (2016), (Eds.). *Nigeria’s Ungoverned Spaces: Studies in Security, Terrorism and Governance* (Obafemi Awolowo University Press, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, 2016).
- 28) Saith, R. (2001). *Capabilities: The concept and its operation*. Retrieved from Schiller, R. B. (2008). *The Economics of poverty and discrimination*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Peason Prentice Hall.
- 29) Schatz, E., & Schiffer, K. (2008). *Marginalization, social inclusion and health*. Obtained 22 January 2024. <http://www/correlation-net.org>.
- 30) Sen, A. (1985). *Commodity capabilities*. New Delhi, India: Oxford University Press.
- 31) This Day; 2019
- 32) UNDP, (2017) *Africa’s Unique Vulnerability to Violent Extremism* (United Nations Development Programme, New York, USA, 2017).
- 33) Whitehead, M., & Dahigren, G. (2006). *Leveling up: discussion paper on concepts and principles for tackling social inequalities in health*. Obtained on 22 January 2024. <https://www.eurohealth.net.eu> 06-04-2022
- 34) World Food Program, WFP (2023); UNHCR (2023). Obtained 15 August 2023
- 35) www.dailytrust.com.ng: Obtained 23 November 2023
- 36) www.vanguard.com; Obtained 4 February 2024)
- 37) www.vanguardngr.com; 2024. Obtained 31 January 2024
- 38) www.researchgate.net; 2024. Obtained 28 January 2024
- 39) www.faapa.info; 2019. Obtained 19 February 2024
- 40) www.ploughshares.com Project Ploughshares. (n.d.). *Armed Conflict*. Obtained on 8 February 2024
- 41) www.cbn.gov.ng; 2024. Obtained 20 March 2024.
- 42) www.uclg-aspac.org; 2021. Obtained 15 April 2024
- 43) www.fao.org. Obtained 14 April 2024